

Research Article

Two-Thirds Majority, Personalization of Power and Absolute Decline: An Observation on Bangladesh Politics

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ABSTRACT

Needless to say, the constitution of Bangladesh ensured a two-thirds majority in parliament, granting the ruling party complete liberty in implementing power. The majority has both options: to be a good ruler or an anarchist. In the National Election since independence, a majority and an absolute majority have both been achieved. Despite having many grumbles against the election and governance, the perception hardly exists that overconfidence grows with a two-thirds majority among these regimes, creating personalization of power to the President or the Prime Minister. No doubt, the way state machinery was governed during those tenures created not only an imbalance and deficit of trust in Bangladesh's politics, but also paved the way for a gradual transition to a dictator or fascist regime. The activities of those governments' evident personalization of power and an absolute fall. Literature from secondary sources and news from the National and International media are the core information of this exploratory observation. However, based on print and electronic content analysis, the research found that the overwhelming majority created personalization of power, and this uncontrolled power made the regime fascist and finally led to an absolute fall.

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Introduction

Bangladesh is a country that has been thirsting for independence and social justice since its inception as a part of the United Pakistan in 1947. Movements for socio-economic emancipation and political autonomy led birth of the country in 1971. Bangladesh inherited the pride of achieving a two-thirds majority in the election before its birth in 1970. But the experience became hostile as the military ruler of Pakistan did not cooperate to form a government. Later, in independent Bangladesh, the hope of the nation was abandoned several times over more than 50 years. Since independence, political trust deficit, ideological domination and rigidity, debate between secularism and Islamization, pro or anti-India-Pakistan collaboration, Liberation War and anti-Liberation War sentiment, extreme level of corruption, extra-judicial affairs, abuse of law enforcement bodies, zero-sum game, and personalization of power are some phenomena in the politics of Bangladesh. Demographically, the Bangali is a homogeneous and a rebel nation. Lack of political consensus created an embankment on the way to the nation's development. The Constitution of Bangladesh ushered in the opportunity for the government to utilize its optimum power in governance in a legitimate way. According to the Constitution of Bangladesh, a government with a two-thirds majority deserves to do anything lawfully, whatever it wants. This black cheque can be the best weapon for such a government, either to do the best or the worst for the country. However, the history of Bangladesh's regimes is very abject. Here, the nation is either willingly or unwillingly abusing power. Most of the time during the transitions of power through national polls, all the parties endeavored to achieve a two-thirds majority (most of the time either by electoral manipulation or by domination of the opposition). A total of 8 two-thirds majority among 12 national polls was achieved (Figure 1). But in real points of view, all those regimes, the Prime Minister or the President, by all means, were engaged to grasp state power. Moreover, neo-patrimonialism in politics handed over the position of party head, parliament head, and state head to the same person, which was unchecked in the major political parties, the Bangladesh Awami League (BAL) and the Bangladesh Nationalist Party (BNP).

Literature from the previous study found that this unchecked imbalance created personalization of power. Information adopted from this exploratory observation, endeavored to find out that none of those overwhelming majorities in the parliament survived the full tenure unless they became a dictator. However, finally, those dictatorial regimes also ended either through assassination or uprooted by mass upsurge.

This is basically an exploratory observation. To meet the basic findings of the research, it extensively concentrated on the literature from secondary sources. Special concentration given on the scholarly articles, distinguished reports from different recognized authorities and organizations. To meet the research question and find the research gap, the study emphasized several printed and electronic national and international media. Later on, the historical background of the two-thirds majority and personalization of politics were narrated and analyzed, which seeks to explore how various regimes monopolized the state power for personalization, and also followed the analysis of contemporary party politics of Bangladesh. Finally, it met the findings that those regimes led to an absolute fall.

Literature Review

Two-Thirds Majority: A Glimpse into National Polls of Bangladesh

The constitution of Bangladesh not only paved the way for forming a government but also ensured the power and functions of the parliament and government. The national election is the most transparent way of forming a legitimate government in Bangladesh. Since the independence of the country, there have been 12 national elections held in Bangladesh, and the 12th national election was held on the 7th January 2024. According to the office of the Election Commission, Bangladesh Awami League (BAL) won more than two-thirds majority in the election and formed the government. Out of 300 constituencies, BAL won 222 (BSS, 2024). It was the 8th two-thirds majority in the parliament among 12 national polls and 5th time for BAL. Rest 3 times 8th two-thirds majority was achieved by the Bangladesh Nationalist Party (BNP) twice in 1979 and 1996 (Feb), and once by the Bangladesh Jatiya Party (BJP) in 1988. According to the report of the Business Standard, as shown in Table 1, immediately after the independence of Bangladesh, in the 1st national polls, BAL won 293 seats and the remaining 7 by others, as there were no more political opponents at that time. In the second national polls, held in 1979 after a huge change of political episode in 1975, BNP won 207, where the popularity of BAL had sharply declined by 254 seats, and the representation of other minor parties and individuals increased by 47. Fourth, Sixth, and Tenth elections in Bangladesh might be considered as non-participatory, as the main opposition and populist parties did not contest the elections.

Table 1

Jatiya Sangsad Seat Distribution over the Years

National Election/Year	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th	7 th	8 th	9 th	10 th	11 th	12 th
Political Party (won)	1973	1979	1986	1988	1991	1996 (Feb)	1996 (Jun)	2001	2008	2014	2018	2024
BAL	293	39	76	0	88	0	146	62	230	234	258	222
BNP	0	207	0	0	140	278	111	193	30	0	6	0
Jatiya Party	0	0	153	251	35	0	32	14	27	34	23	11
Jamaat Islami	0	0	10	0	18	0	3	17	2	0	0	0
Others	7	54	61	49	19	22	3	14	11	32	13	65

Source: The Business Standard <https://www.tbsnews.net/election-2024>

Fifth, seventh, and eighth national elections are considered the most competitive, participatory, and fair elections in the history of Bangladesh. It can be noted here that from 1991 to 2008, during the tenure that is considered as the second phase of democratic restoration in the political history of Bangladesh, six national elections have been conducted in 1991, 1996-February, 1996-June, 2001, 2008, and 2014 by the Election Commission of Bangladesh. However, four out of these six elections (1991, 1996-June, 2001, and 2008) were comparatively free and fair,

which has been certified by the national and international election observers, including electronic and print media. Later on, BAL formed the government in January 2009 with an absolute majority, but the provision of Care Taker Government (CTG) was abolished by the 15th amendment of the constitution in 2011, despite serious disagreement and remonstrations of opposition political parties. (Mollah, 2016). The 10th, 11th, and 12th national elections were held under the ruling BAL in accordance with constitutional requirements. However, BNP-led allies totally boycotted the 10th and 12th national polls but took part in the 11th. The major opposition party, BNP, and its allies had boycotted the polls, alleging that a free and fair election was not possible under the Sheikh Hasina-led government. (DDNews, 2024). Among these three consecutive national elections, including the 9th BAL led by a two-thirds majority despite a huge controversy arising over the election mechanism and engineering. From 2008 to 2024, for about one and a half decades, BAL ruled over the parliament and the government with more than an absolute majority, which led to the PM, Parliament Leader, and the BAL party chief having unprecedented power.

Methodology

This study employs an exploratory qualitative research design anchored in systematic analysis of secondary sources to examine the relationship between constitutional supermajorities (specifically two-thirds parliamentary majorities), the personalization of executive power, and episodes of regime decline in the political history of Bangladesh. Given the historical and institutional nature of the inquiry, the research relies exclusively on documented evidence in the public domain.

Data Collection

All data were derived from secondary sources that provide verified historical records and analysis. These include: Official electoral and statistical records from the Bangladesh Election Commission and authoritative reporting in national media outlets, used to establish exact seat distributions and supermajority outcomes—for example, the 12th parliamentary election held on January 7, 2024, where the ruling Awami League won 224 seats out of 300 contested under contentious conditions.

Peer-reviewed scholarly literature on political institutions, executive power dynamics, and authoritarian transitions, offering interpretive frameworks for understanding constitutional change and institutional balance. Print and electronic media reports from recognized national and international outlets, providing contemporaneous accounts of constitutional amendments, electoral conduct, and governance behavior. Policy papers, expert commentary, and legal analyses focused on constitutional provisions such as Article 70, which enforces strict party discipline in parliament, and major amendments like the 15th Amendment that abolished the constitutionally mandated caretaker government system.

Analytical Framework

This research adopts a qualitative content analysis approach, organizing material thematically around three core variables:

- i. Incidence of two-thirds parliamentary majorities.
- ii. Manifestations of personalization of power by executive leaders.
- iii. Indicators of regime weakening or collapse.

The analysis unfolds through the following components:

i. ***Chronological Regime Profiling:***

Each national election cycle from the first parliamentary contest of 1973 through to the 12th general election, 2024, was systematically reviewed. Seat distribution data were used to identify instances where supermajorities occurred and to assess subsequent political trajectories. Historical accounts reveal that supermajorities, beginning with the 1973 Awami League victory, enabled constitutional changes with profound institutional impact.

ii. ***Institutional Impact Assessment:***

Constitutional amendments and legal reforms enacted by governments with supermajority checks were examined to assess their impact on the major organ of government. Notably, constitutional changes, such as the 2011 abolition of the caretaker government provision, have had lasting implications for electoral credibility and institutional independence.

iii. ***Regime Behavior Analysis:***

Secondary accounts of governance practices—such as opposition suppression, changes to electoral administration, and use of state coercive instruments—were assessed to understand the patterns of executive consolidation following supermajority rule. This included scrutiny of Article 70's effects on parliamentary oversight and dissent.

Personalization of Power: Concept in the Light of Bangladesh

In recent times, the personalization of power in political phenomena is a very evident worldwide trend, which is why in many countries, a democratic leader, even with legitimacy, appears as an autocratic leader and tends to become fascist. Especially after the transformation of traditional party government, a radical shift in power from collective to individual actors and institutions has followed in several political systems. A very common narrative among the world's political leaders is that they need collective powers to weaken the parties inside, and in such an environment, democracy would never recover. Political leadership in Bangladesh has struggled to personalize state power since independence. All successive governments in Bangladesh have tirelessly tried to control the judiciary under the executive every time (Islam, 2013). In a democratic context, political leaders are the primary focus, and they endeavor to establish a relationship with citizens, directly or indirectly, and to exert domination over governmental actions. That's why governmental courses are focused on dominating the legislature through accelerating new ways of self-directed law-making (Musella & Rullo, 2023). Personalism is a time-dependent characteristic of dictatorial regimes. Thus,

personalization of power is understood as one of the significant characteristics seen in different strengths across all types of authoritarian regimes, varying throughout the tenure of a dictator. Personalism, according to several scholars, is broadly explained as one of the characteristics of dictatorships that can function distinctly over time. Among them, some manage to seize control of decision-making and political recruitments at the cost of their associates and dominate administrations. In Bangladesh, personalization of power emerged since its inception. According to some of the constitutional experts, Article 70 of the constitution “was framed after much thought to ensure stability and strengthen parliamentary democracy.” By way of maintaining party discipline, Article 70 ensures a healthy and stable parliamentary democracy, which is important to ensure the stability of the government oracy, which is important to ensure the stability of the government (Mondal, 2005).

With the intention of including Article 70, the freedom of the cabinet chosen by the citizens has been kept away. This law basically hampers the institutionalization of the parliamentary democracy. According to the view of the Lawyers and Jurists, ‘Under the anti-defection or anti-floor-crossing law, the government and the executive are in a position where they can enjoy dictatorship, as there is no one from the government to protest or vote against. As a result, the government, as it is not going to be answerable to any of the members or the legislature, can pass any unethical bill which can be harmful to the country, and there is no one to object or vote against.

According to the 4th Amendment to the Constitution of Bangladesh, the President was given the power to control the lower courts, which thoroughly violates the basic structure of the Constitution, as the change spoils the independence of the lower judiciary. In the observation of Shakhawat Liton through the verdict of the Supreme Court regarding the 16th Amendment of the Constitution, it was claimed that the 4th Amendment violates the basic structure of the Constitution, and therefore, this substitution of the word 'President' is ultra vires the Constitution. The 4th Amendment to the Constitution of Bangladesh demolished the parliamentary system of democracy and introduced a presidential form of government, and proceeded to form a one-party political system. It established the Bangladesh Krishak Sramik Awami League (BAKSAL), which proceeded towards the empowerment of a one-man presidential system, ignoring public mandate. Personalization of politics inside the parliament, government, and in the party system was established as the same person holds all these three chairs. A two-thirds majority in the first national election of 1973 helped the party chair and the president to bring this amendment into effect in the parliament and the changes in the political system and governance, which ultimately created an authoritarian system and led to dire ramifications in 1975 (Research Directorate, Immigration and Refugee Board, 1991). In the 4th National Election held in 1988, Jatiya Party (JP) led by HM Ershad won 251 out of the total 300 parliamentary seats (Table 1). Though major political parties, both AL and BNP, boycotted the election, JP was widely criticized for its unashamed rigging and fraud. Obtaining a two-thirds majority in parliament helped the president in the personalization of power and later became a dictator. And the ultimate ramification was the resignation of severe students and mass upsurge of 1990 (Uddin & Rahman, 2018).

The Bangladesh Awami League (BAL), led by Sheikh Hasina, came to power through the 9th national election in 2008 with a two-thirds majority (Table 1) and maintained the same dominance in the 10th, 11th, and 12th national polls. A major complaint emerged in national and international media about the transparency of the election, as the nonpartisan caretaker system for power transition was abolished through the 15th amendment to the constitution. Several experts claimed that this abolition destroyed democracy, the election process, and the independence of the judiciary (Sarkar & Rahman, 2024). Consequently, national elections held after these amendments were challenged as being fair and transparent, and major political parties, including BNP, either boycotted the election or were victims of election engineering. This unholy legitimacy consolidated the personal power of the Prime Minister above that of the parliament. The following three consecutive regimes of Sheikh Hasina operated without meaningful political engagement. Legal frameworks were used to legitimize and reinforce the power of the authority. Though Hasina's regimes were justified by her as a torchbearer, in reality, Hasina's governance was more institutionalized and strategic.

In some opinions, like Abu Salek Khan and others, throughout some newspapers and writings, it was explained that the entire politics of Sheikh Hasina was traumatized for losing her father and family members, and that is why she deluded politics and institutions with this trauma, which later transformed into rebellion, shifting personal insecurity into national insecurity. This tendency rose a narrative among the politicians of BAL that Bangladesh would descend into chaos without the leadership of Hasina. That is why, in her governance of a decade and a half, all power of the state moved around her, and there was no authority other than her. It created challenges to democracy. (Khan, 2024)¹ opined to the Prothom Alo that, *'Mujibur Rahman faced severe criticism for suppressing opposition, which included imprisonment, torture, and murder, under the pretext of protecting the state from "anti-national" forces. Similarly, Sheikh Hasina's government often justifies its repression of dissent and opposition parties as essential for safeguarding democracy and independence, albeit in direct contradiction to democratic principles.'*

Bangladesh Nationalist Party (BNP) Vice-Chairman Advocate Nitai Roy Chowdhury expressed to BSS News (Roy, 2024) - *"After the rigged elections of 2008, the Awami League government destroyed the constitution by enacting many new laws and amending the constitution at will."*

On the eve of her loss of power, she was considered a fascist, and the reason for her being dictatorial is nothing but her extreme level of empowerment. According to the view of Osmani (2025)² through the Daily Star, *'We should, therefore, delete all references to fascism in this document and describe Sheikh Hasina's fallen regime for what it was—a brutally tyrannical autocratic regime built upon megalomania, selfishness, and unbridled greed for power.'* Personalization of power led Hasina to deform and demonize herself into a brutal dictator and tyrant, tearing up the nation, rag and piece disintegration, especially since 2009 (Khan, 2021).

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Findings and Discussion

Absolute Decline: Observation on the Regimes of Bangladesh

If we give a glimpse of all the national elections held in Bangladesh (Table 1) and the literature review above, we find that two-thirds of the majority in polls were achieved either in the absence of a strong competitor or through gross manipulation. Constitutionally, the regime that is formed with a two-thirds majority has led to the personalization of power to the President or Prime Minister. The country received this unfortunate destiny on the eve of the inception of the newly born country. Lord Acton, a British historian of the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, stated the famous quote, - *Power tends to corrupt; absolute power corrupts absolutely*³.

The overwhelming majority in the Bangladesh parliament tends towards absolute power, which ultimately leads to absolute fall. The Mujib regime, the Ershad regime, and the longest regimes of Hasina are evident in this ramification. Spanish revolutionary Buenaventura Durruti stated, “*When the bourgeoisie sees that power is slipping out of its hands, it brings up fascism to hold onto its privileges.*”

Among all national elections, in the 1st, 2nd, 4th, and 9th to 12th polls, a two-thirds majority was achieved, and in most cases, personalization of power privileges fascism, and in all four regimes (9th to 12th, the same regime), the destiny was absolute fall or assassination. Before and during the time of Liberation War of Bangladesh Mujib was the voice of the people of Bangladesh but very soon he lost the touch with them as he became failure to control corruption in the party and administration, arbitrarily changed the constitution and made himself the President with all power, declared emergency dissolved the politics of all other parties, stopped the freedom of media, postponed fundamental rights.

A former minister, ambassador, and journalist, Enayetullah Khan, stated (Chowdhury, 2024) - “*His strolls around the corridor of power at times drew pity; he frowned at straight talk; he tried to destroy dissidents with his wrath. He loved the nation, yet he betrayed it. He had to pay with his life.*”

Mujib grabbed the state power in his own hands and accepted an autocratic form of government, which was terrible in a real sense. Soon, it fired back at him, and to control the situation, he formed Rakkhi Bahini (a personal and private security force), which was a brush-off to the state army that fought for the Liberation War. Eventually, conspiracies of coups were raised, and finally, he was assassinated.

The second national poll in Bangladesh was also a two-thirds majority competing with the major political party of that time, BAL, though it was held under the president's rule. This regime also faced a brutal ending within two years in office. However, Zia's assassination is widely claimed as a misunderstanding and a conspiracy within the military. But for our research, we can find the similarity that two-thirds majority and absolute decline.

³ <https://www.dictionary.com/browse/power-tends-to-corrupt-absolute-power-corrupts-absolutely>

HM Ershad was in power for the longest time in the history of 20th-century Bangladesh. Under his presidency, the 3rd and 4th national polls of Bangladesh were held, where in the 4th national poll (held in 1988), his political party achieved a two-thirds majority. Soon, Ershad reached the peak of his position, and to bring popularity, he took some initiatives to draw the attention of the common people. But it was too tempestuous to accept him as a lifelong leader as nepotism and corruption increased, and the President compromised to a great extent just for the sake of being reelected in power. This helped him personalize power and led towards anarchy. Very soon, BAL and BNP appeared on the same platform to demolish his power, and it turned into a mass upsurge with the involvement of the students of Dhaka University and other educational institutions countrywide (The Irish Times, 2019).

The movement reached a momentum in October 1990 when the student movement reached the pioneer position, and the ever-divided opposition parties made an alliance against Ershad. The government responded wrongly and declared an emergency, around 50 to 100 deaths and 3000 injuries (Directorate, 1991). Finally, the President resigned, and an absolute decline of the regime happened within two years of forming the government through a two-thirds majority.

Sheikh Hasina, daughter of late President Sheikh Mujibur Rahman, got involved in politics long after the death of Mujib. Soon she became the sole person of BAL and formed a government in 1996 for the first time. But her personalization of power was evident soon after gaining power in 2008 for the second time. Since then, she has remained Prime Minister for four consecutive regimes in the history of Bangladesh. But the whole journey was much more pleasant, neither for her dominion nor for the nation. A lot of chaos and chasm were recorded within her one and a half decades of power. Throughout her entire regime, she and her political party, BAL, capitalized on the legacy of the Liberation War, grasping the sole role of the voice of war sentiment. The domination of this legacy was abused to create a single-party democracy. Soon, the distance between the political parties of other sentiment and ideology became wider due to a trust deficit among the politicians created by the name of the belief in the liberation war and anti-liberation war. With the passage of time, Sheikh Hasina became vindictive and executed several political leaders, accusing as war criminals (Petersen & Rahman, 2023). However, several complaints are there regarding her way of justice by the name of International Crime Tribunals. By the name of religious extremist, thousands of politicians from the opposition were imprisoned. These types of activities created a social clan in the history of Bangladesh. Ali Riaz, a professor at Illinois State University, stated, '*Hasina's regime embodied 'the arrogance of autocracy'*' (Abdullah, 2024).

All these political activities created a border among the nation, and Hasina was capable of materializing her autocratic agenda due to her being empowered through absolute precedence in the parliament. After her first two-thirds majority achieved in the 9th national poll held in 2008, onward, Hasina started to consolidate the power of the key institutions of the state, the judiciary, law enforcement bodies, bureaucracy and administration, Anti-Corruption Commission, and so on. She made these bodies vulnerable through her political one-handed domination. Her political ironic domination in all respects was the ingredient of her personalization of power (Rizve, 2024).

Since the last three-decade mass upsurge, non-violent protests have become a more popular route to democracy. Though protest mobilization succeeds in collapsing dictatorships sometimes, it promotes civil conflict and failed states even more (Chin et al., 2022). Sheikh Haina's autocratic regime from 2009 to 2024 destroyed the democracy of Bangladesh. As she achieved a two-thirds majority in all consecutive national polls held under her power, she became desperate from 2014 to 2024. Electoral manipulation, authoritarian amendment to the constitution, extreme control and suppression of the opposition, restricted press and media were the weapons of Hasina to become a dictator. To stop the rights of oppositions, Hasina used to use the state institutions, the judiciary, and law enforcement bodies, which she gained control over. (Aljazeera, 2024). Her arbitrary detention, extrajudicial killings by law-enforcing bodies, Rapid Action Battalion RAB and the police, state-patronized abduction by them, and execution of oppositions made her cruel and dictatorial. Turmoil in the educational institutions and streets, and a mass upsurge just before her exile from power, finally led to absolute decline. (OHCHR, 2025). It was recorded that a huge, remarkable infrastructural development like Padma Bridge, Dhaka Metro Rail, 3rd Terminal of Shah Jalal International Airport, and many others took place in her tenure, but due to her stubborn autocratic attitude and failure to measure the pulse of the nation, finally, absolute decline occurred. (HRRC, 2025).

Limitations

This study's reliance on secondary sources means that findings depend on the accuracy and completeness of existing documentation. There were no primary interviews, surveys, or fieldwork conducted. The analysis also acknowledges the challenge of isolating causality in complex political phenomena; however, the recurring pattern of supermajority preceding centralization of power is robustly supported by the documentary record.

Conclusion

To conclude whether two-thirds majority and personalization of power survive in Bangladesh or ultimately the regimes decline can be a subject matter for further broad analysis. But the nexus that is made through this explorative observation found that, although Sheikh Hasina's recent regime, which was a combination of four consecutive regimes formed with two-thirds, apparently survived for one and a half decades, all other regimes made by the same, never lasted more than two years in the history of Bangladesh. Apart from Hasina's longest regime, the first two-thirds majority-winning regime of Sheikh Mujibur Rahman turned to autonomy despite not having that many competitive challenges from the political opposition. His personalization of power transformed him from a *state man* to a person, as if *he were the state*. This unbounded power could not rescue him, but rather brought him to extreme ramifications in 1975.

Later, Ziaur Rahman and HM Ershad both were Military rulers, though after demilitarization, they were not in the same grievance, but couldn't survive after achieving a two-thirds majority. President Zia had to accept the cue and was murdered, and HM Ershad, though he was in power for 9 years, had to accept the title of an anarchist and was thrown out of the chair with the students and a mass upsurge of 1990. Further, in the election of February 1996, BNP led by

Begum Khaleda Zia also won a two-thirds majority, but constituted the shortest time regime in the history of Bangladesh, which resigned and dissolved the parliament by herself, fulfilling some parliamentary and constitutional challenges demanded by her opponents.

Hasina was the longest-serving Prime Minister in the history of Bangladesh, who formed several regimes with a two-thirds majority from 2008 to 2024. The findings of this research could have been different if she had been capable of transferring her regimes with a participatory and fair election, rather than having to accept the shameful title and destiny of Fascist in the history of Bangladesh and escaping the country. Personalization of Power in Hasina's Regimes knew no bounds, and her examples of cruelty superseded the history of Bangladesh. Accused of using her administration, law-enforcing body, special wings like RAB, BD, DGFI, and many others for abducting and killing opposition members, abuse of the Judiciary for executing the convicted politicians of opposite mentality, politicization of state machineries at every level, let her personalization of power be unprecedented in the history of Bangladesh (Mahmud, 2024). Despite this, Hasina was afraid of giving an election under a non-party caretaker government, for which her political party, BAL, was demanding, removed this system of power transformation and called for an election under her rule. Gradual power-grasping addicted her so notoriously that the trust deficit in Bangladesh politics became wider and created a zero-sum game. (Islam, 2013). Nevertheless, ultimately, nothing could rescue her; she had to escape against the students and mass upsurge of 2024 by abandoning her companion and party, which faced thousands of challenges.

The research undertaken under time constraints against the focused findings of the study is a very recent issue, though rooted in history. And hence, scarcity of established work is also another limitation. However, it may be considered as the inception of further study.

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